

NPT – A Success Story Evolving From Teamwork and Innovation

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ABSTRACT The Network Planning Terminal (NPT) is a new battlefield automated system designed to efficiently integrate network planning and management, frequency management, communications engineering, and electronic warfare threat analysis for the Army's Mobile Subscriber Equipment. The NPT program is managed by Program Manager, Joint Tactical Area Communications Systems (Provisional). The development team includes the Electromagnetic Compatibility Analysis Center (ECAC) and the Communications-Electronics Command (CECOM). ECAC is responsible for systems integration, while ECAC and CECOM share the responsibility for hardware acquisition and software development. Fielding of the NPT is imminent.

This paper provides a functional description of the NPT and describes both the teamwork between internal Government organizations and the systems integration process that resulted in the success of the NPT program. This success highlights the power of Total Quality Management based working groups, the involvement of soldiers, and the cooperative efforts of RD&E programs within the CECOM Research, Development and Engineering Center and ECAC that have provided the baseline NPT product that fits the available resources of the Program Manager. Companion papers describe some of the technical aspects of NPT.

Introduction

The Network Planning Terminal (NPT) evolved out of Program Manager (PM), Joint Tactical Area Communications Systems (JTACS [Provisional]) efforts to continually improve the products that were fielded for Mobile Subscriber Equipment (MSE). There was general recognition that battlefield spectrum management (BSM) and network management systems initially fielded with MSE could be significantly improved. The MSE Frequency Utilization Resource Integration and Engineering System (FURIES) was initiated in 1989 to address the BSM/

network management requirements enhancements. In 1991, this program was renamed "Network Planning Terminal" as a result of the integration of network planning products developed from the MSE System Performance Model [1].

This paper provides a functional description of the NPT and describes both the teamwork between internal Government organizations and the systems integration process that have contributed to the success of the NPT program. This success highlights the power of total quality management (TQM) based working groups, the involvement of soldiers, and the cooperative efforts of RD&E programs within the U.S. Army Communications-Electronics Command (CECOM) Research, Development and Engineering Center (RDEC) and the Electromagnetic Compatibility Analysis Center (ECAC) that have provided the baseline NPT product that fits the available resources of the PM. This paper describes the use of interdisciplinary engineering working groups that has streamlined the process of concept development to final design from years to months. This paper also reviews ECAC's support to PM JTACS (Provisional) in the integration process that has brought software and hardware components from diverse sources together to operate as a unit. Finally, this paper provides an overview of the aggressive, continuing improvement program that is based on customer feedback, engineering working groups, and innovative project management.

This paper serves as an introduction to three other MILCOM '93 papers. One describes the contribution of the MSE System Performance Model to the network planning portion of the NPT [1]; another describes the path reliability model incorporated in the NPT [2]; and the last describes the development of the climate factor parameter that is critical to the path reliability model [3].

NPT Description

The MSE NPT is a new battlefield automated system that provides major advances in communications engineering and network planning capabilities. Included in the NPT are threat and

path reliability models, corps and multi-corps communications network planning, spectrum management, and CD-ROM maps and terrain elevations. NPT provides automated data communications packages for tactical, fixed station, and commercial data transfer using the MSE packet switch, X.25, modems (secure and nonsecure), and local area networks; database retrieval packages, artificial intelligence features for frequently requested services, and word processing and spreadsheet utilities. Area common user systems other than MSE can be accommodated. The NPT provides the U.S. Army with a new capability to plan reliable networks for deployment anywhere in the world.

The NPT is used to assist in planning an MSE network and in modifying a network plan during operations. It is structured to address in an integrated manner:

- Network laydown planning
- Path reliability engineering
- Frequency management
- Electronic warfare (EW) threat analysis
- Link acceptance

Network laydown planning includes:

- Automatic specification of available assets for each Army subscriber unit
- Automatic placement of assets to create an initial network based on subscriber requirements and location
- Dynamic replanning of the network to support unit moves during battle
- Management of subscriber and exercise databases
- Interactive network modification
- Automatic node and Radio Access Unit (RAU) site optimization.

Path reliability engineering includes:

- Line-of-sight (LOS) propagation reliability analysis
- Link optimization
- High-elevation identification
- Path profiling
- Path-loss calculations
- Fade margin determination based on actual location and time of deployment
- Area radio coverage.

Frequency management includes:

- Robust frequency assignment techniques for all MSE radios
- Efficient spectrum utilization
- Cosite and intersite analysis
- Mobile Subscriber Radio-telephone Terminal (MSRT)/RAU frequency plans
- Automated frequency transfer.

EW threat analysis includes:

- Definition of jammer platforms

- Path reliability impact evaluation.

Link acceptance includes:

- Analysis of measured link initialization data
- Acceptance or reengineering of links as required.

NPT advances in the state of the art include:

- Intuitive state-of-the-art soldier-machine interface using pull-down menus and point-and-click windows over topographic maps
- Automation and integration of communications engineering functions
- A communications engineering process to guide the use of link and network design tools in accordance with the latest MSE system procedures
- Path reliability as a user-selectable link-design value
- Automatic worldwide geoclimatic factors to account for variability of propagation conditions.

The NPT software is hosted on 486-PC architecture running under the SCO Unix operating system. NPT operation and user interaction are color-graphics-oriented, achieved via X-Window interfaces. Map images are formed from Defense Mapping Agency digital information using the TerraCAMMS Display Manager. Networks and threats are displayed over a map background. Link reliability is color-coded. Mouse click-and-drag, database, and keyboard inputs are combined to simplify operation. Figure 1 is a screen example showing a network section on a map display. The NPT is open architecture by design

Figure 1. Sample of NPT Screen Display
(Actual Display Is In Color)

and is delivered with complete Department of Defense (DoD)-STD 2167A software documentation. The system includes new equipment training (NET) and a total-package fielding process. Post-deployment software support procedures are in place.

Streamlining the Development Process

A major challenge PM JTACS (Provisional) and the R&D community had to meet was to concurrently develop concepts in the technology base leading to products while also focusing on the evolution of MSE as a fielded system. The computer software and hardware evolutions that were and still are occurring present a major challenge to the NPT product development team. For a product to be a success, it must quickly go from concept to the customer, meet customer expectation, and be continually improved. In order to meet this challenge, PMJTACS (Provisional) has chosen to use internal Government development teams. It is important to understand that each of the teams is focused on developing engineering concepts for products that can be integrated into a final product for the soldiers. There are four development teams discussed in this paper: (1) Army battlefield spectrum management and engineering (ABSME), (2) line-of-sight propagation reliability (LOSPR), (3) modeling and simulation (M&S), and (4) network management automation and integration (NMAI). All four development teams are funded with CECOM RDEC resources out of the BSM and communication M&S mission. These resources are being complemented by PM JTACS (Provisional) in order to continue the development of concepts into fieldable products. These teams are also developing enhancements to be added to the MSE system M&S process. The teams assist the PM regarding application of tactical planning and operation procedures for soldiers. A key goal is to assure maximum performance from the complex communications systems that the PM has fielded. Further, the simulation process is used to assist PM in the evaluation of potential product improvements and the management of the test and evaluation mission.

The integration of the technology base with PM-focused resources is a major factor in reducing the time it takes to field the product as well as in assuring soldier satisfaction with the product. All of the development teams use the tools of TQM. Brainstorming, group dynamics, and the multidisciplinary nature of the teams have all contributed to the success of the NPT program.

Spectrum Management Team

The ABSME program evolved out of the need to improve the Army's ability to address the continued increase in complexity of the electromagnetic environments in which systems had to operate during the 1970s. The team was originated in 1979 by the Development Laboratories at Fort Monmouth, New Jersey, and included ECAC participation. The mission of the program is to generate R&D concepts and develop prototype software.

This team has been successful in developing software products that have been used by all the military services as well as customers outside the DoD world. Most of the BSM products in NPT evolved from this effort. These products must satisfy many criteria in order to provide network connectivity. An example of a ABSME product used in NPT is the Tactical Frequency

Assignment Module (TACFAM), which, among other things, generates compatible frequency assignments for UHF/SHF multichannel radio networks.

Propagation Reliability Team

Operation Desert Storm deployment of tactical LOS radio links as used with MSE and other TRI-TAC switching systems raised the issue of link reliability in stressing propagation climates. The environment encountered in Southwest Asia is known to be difficult for LOS radio propagation.

As a result of questions and concerns PM JTACS (Provisional) had with regard to the impacts on network reliability, particularly with extension nodes and range extension of the backbone links being utilized for battlefield automated systems data transmission, the LOSPR team was formed in April 1991. The LOSPR is a CECOM RDEC/PM JTACS (Provisional)-sponsored team with participation from the Army Research Laboratory (ARL). The team has consulted with scientists in the Canadian Government, the Defense Communications Systems Agency, ECAC, and the U.S. Army Test and Evaluation Command. This team's primary mission is to investigate and develop solutions to problems encountered by soldiers using LOS radios in difficult climates as well as the global battlefields of the future. Currently, this team has developed a model that links fade margin to link distance and environment. The model also establishes link reliabilities based on distance, frequency, and environment. This model allows LOS planners to design links that better achieve desired performance goals [2,3]. Figure 2 is a conceptual example of the results of using the model to analyze the path reliability of candidate links. The open circles represent the

Figure 2. Network Laydown Reliability Example (Simplified Redrawing Of Screen)

locations of switches, extension nodes, and remote RAUs. In this case, two of the links have unacceptable reliability and will have to be reengineered using tools contained in NPT. The actual NPT display shows color-coded links according to their predicted path reliability: green for satisfactory, amber for marginal, and red for unacceptable (link is inoperable). The soldier clicks displayed link or site elements to perform the engineering or obtain further information.

The team has also provided recommendations for improved operating procedures [4] and is working on changes to training material as well as automated products that can be integrated into currently fielded link engineering tools. The primary goal is to ensure that operators and planners have the latest data available to maximize their current LOS capability.

Modeling and Simulation Team

During the initial fielding process of MSE, it became apparent to PMJTACS (Provisional) that a considerable modeling and simulation effort was required to support the test and evaluation process as well as to assess future product improvement efforts. In 1987, PM JTACS (Provisional) funded CECOM to review what could be done to accomplish this. As a result, an internal CECOM M&S team undertook several modeling tasks that resulted in an MSE System Performance Model known as MSE SPM [1]. This model remains in place today and has been used by PM JTACS (Provisional) and other customers to support the major functions of: (1) prediction of MSE system battlefield performance, (2) product improvement trade-off analysis, and (3) development of automated products for soldiers. The last of these functions is the major focus of this paper. An example of an NPT product from the M&S team is the EW threat analysis capability, which allows the network planner to define and position EW threat laydowns and automatically calculate the effects on the path reliability of each of the MSE links in a network. The results are immediately displayed for visual examination. Sites and links can then be modified to improve the network's response to the EW threat so that all reliability requirements are met. Figure 3 is a conceptual example of the application of this capability. The open circles represent the locations of switches, extension nodes, and remote RAUs. A jammer has been positioned and characterized; its effect is to change the predicted reliability from satisfactory to unacceptable on two links. These links will have to be reengineered using other NPT tools in order to obtain an acceptable predicted path reliability.

Soldier Involvement

The soldier has been directly involved in automating the BSM process. Initially, the Army Tactical Frequency Engineering System (ATFES) provided software to a European test bed. The test bed consisted of a vertical slice of signal units from theater through division. The units used the software in their exercises and provided feedback on its accuracy and usefulness. They also identified new needs for improvements to assist them

in their communication system planning and frequency assignment processes.

When the soldier identified a need for a new or significantly improved product, the troops would meet with the sponsor and the software development team to define the requirements. The team would then document the requirements and design the initial concept of the product. The users would then review and critique the software development plan; this would refine either the requirements or the planned products or both. After software was prepared but before it was given to the user, it was tested in a "red team" approach, in an attempt to find fatal flaws, before actual testing and use in exercises. The users were afforded an opportunity, at any stage in the software development process, to obtain progress reports on the efforts. Once the products were successfully tested and accepted by the users in the European test bed, the software was made available to other users and project management programs.

Figure 3. Example of Jammer Effect on Path Reliability
(Simplified Redrawing of Screen)

The soldier also played a key role in identifying the need for an improved tactical LOS propagation reliability model. Feedback data corroborating the existence of significant link propagation problems and degraded link reliability during Operation Desert Storm were obtained during visits to two returned units, the 35th Signal Brigade at Fort Bragg, North Carolina, and the 57th Signal Battalion at Fort Hood, Texas [5]. These soldiers also identified a need for MSE link reliabilities greater than the approved 90-percent design point. For single-thread links a reliability approaching 100 percent was requested.

Systems Integration

ECAC has supported PM JTACS (Provisional) in the systems integration process since the inception of NPT. ECAC's involvement began with the development of the system specifications. During development, ECAC has provided support in software integration, the selection and acquisition of hardware, and the development of the logistics support package. ECAC's support will continue through fielding and post-deployment support. In addition to providing software components to address spectrum management requirements, ECAC has integrated these components with other software and hardware components from CECOM and commercial sources to provide a complete system ready for fielding.

The ECAC Software Development Library (SDL) is central to the software integration process. The SDL is maintained by a configuration management team. All documents, source code, executables, databases, and system data files delivered for integration into NPT are first registered in the SDL. These deliveries come from either CECOM, the ECAC development team, or commercial sources. Once registered in the SDL, new software components are loaded on a software integration platform for integration with the previously accepted software. A series of tests is performed to verify the proper operation of changes provided by the new software as well as the continued integrity of the system. The software is reviewed from the aspects of system resource utilization and proper database access. The specific data paths and data elements defined in the interface design document are checked for continued accuracy. When integration is successfully completed on the integration platform, the ECAC quality assurance team rechecks that the integrated software is operationally correct by running a series of regression tests. The regression tests are then repeated on the NPT objective hardware platform. Only after successful completion of this test process is the integrated software submitted to the SDL and used to create the next operational baseline in preparation for the formal qualification test that completes the integration process cycle.

Continued Improvement Process

PM JTACS (Provisional) is committed to using the Government development team approach to enhance the NPT. Work is progressing to further automate the functions of the product. The use of NPT as an operational control element of MSE is a major thrust that will provide a fully automated system control center. The individual development teams have been focused on a number of enhancements to the NPT. The areas of enhancement being addressed are:

- Improved reliability models
- Automated system control
- Improved graphics and map products
- Automatic frequency allocation/assignment
- Joint operations functionality
- 24-hour network performance management

- Use of environmental forecasts in planning
- Real-time network performance management
- Battlefield communications simulation.

Network Management Team

One of the major goals of the Program Executive Office for Communications Systems is to expand NPT functionality into the network management and operational control areas. Automated and integrated processes are keys to success in this area. The NMAI team was formed in December 1992 to work this problem. The group is sponsored by CECOM RDEC but includes members from the PM as well as the user community (the U.S. Army Signal Center). The group's mission involves:

- Developing an improved network management process
- Maximizing the use of automation focused on improved efficiency and increased reliability
- Developing network management enhancements for NPT
- Acting as technical network management adviser to one or more PMs.

Summary

The NPT is a new PM JTACS (Provisional) product that provides state-of-the-art capabilities for battlefield network planning and management, frequency management, communications engineering, and EW threat analysis.

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